

EMVA 1288 Data Sheet m0545

This datasheet describes the specification according to the standard 1288 for “Characterization and Presentation of Specification Data for Image Sensors and Cameras of the European Machine Vision Association (EMVA)” (see www.standard1288.org or the *Zenodo EMVA 1288 community*). The measurements were performed with the AEON ACC2b RGB-IR, Release 3, 08.09.2014, SN 0012(). The performance parameters and estimated accuracy of the measurements are described in the technical report for the instrument, its calibration in the corresponding calibration report.

Measurements performed by B Jähne, HCI, Heidelberg University and H Herrmann, AEON

Vendor	Basler
Model	acA3800-14um
Serial number	21529784
Sensor diagonal	7.89 mm
Lens category	C-mount
Resolution	3840 × 2748, 12 bit
Pixel size	1.67 μm × 1.67 μm
Sensor type	CMOS
Shutter type	Rolling
Overlap capabilities	Overlapping
Maximum frame rate	14.0 Hz
Interface type	USB 3.0

Type of data presented	Single
Operation point 1, (page 5)	
Wavelength centroid	466.7 nm
Wavelength FWHM	19.8 nm
Gain, offset	0.0 dB, 24.0
Operation point 2, (page 19)	
Wavelength centroid	532.0 nm
Wavelength FWHM	30.5 nm
Gain, offset	0.0 dB, 24.0
Operation point 3, (page 33)	
Wavelength centroid	629.2 nm
Wavelength FWHM	13.0 nm
Gain, offset	0.0 dB, 24.0
Optional data measured	
None	

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 1

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	0.0 dB, 24.0
Exposure time	50.0 ms	Environmental temperature	22.2°C
Frame rate	14.0 Hz	Camera temperature	30.6°C
Data transfer mode	Mono 12	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	467 nm, 19.8 nm

Quantum efficiency	
η	0.573
Gain	
K (DN/e)	1.833
$1/K$ (e/DN)	0.546
Dark noise & DSNU	
$\sigma_{y,\text{dark}}$ (DN)	6.50
σ_d (e)	3.5
DSNU ₁₂₈₈ (DN)	2.31
DSNU ₁₂₈₈ (e)	1.26
Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU	
SNR _{max}	43
SNR _{max} (dB)	32.7
SNR _{max} (bits)	5.4
$1/\text{SNR}_{\text{max}}$ (%)	2.32
PRNU ₁₂₈₈ (%)	2.547
Nonlinearity	
LE (%)	0.41
Sensitivity & saturation	
$\mu_{p,\text{min}}$ (p)	7.13
$\mu_{p,\text{min}}$ (p/ μm^2)	2.5559
$\mu_{e,\text{min}}$ (e)	4.08
$\mu_{p,\text{sat}}$ (p)	3241
$\mu_{p,\text{sat}}$ (p/ μm^2)	1162
$\mu_{e,\text{sat}}$ (e)	1856
Dynamic range	
DR	455
DR (dB)	53.2
DR (bit)	8.8
Dark current	
$\mu_{c,\text{mean}}$ (DN/s)	-0.65
$\mu_{c,\text{mean}}$ (e/s)	-0.35
$\mu_{c,\text{var}}$ (e/s)	4.97

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 2

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	0.0 dB, 24.0
Exposure time	50.0 ms	Environmental temperature	22.2°C
Frame rate	14.0 Hz	Camera temperature	30.6°C
Data transfer mode	Mono 12	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	532 nm, 30.5 nm

Quantum efficiency	
η	0.436
Gain	
K (DN/e)	1.827
$1/K$ (e/DN)	0.547
Dark noise & DSNU	
$\sigma_{y,\text{dark}}$ (DN)	6.50
σ_d (e)	3.6
DSNU ₁₂₈₈ (DN)	2.31
DSNU ₁₂₈₈ (e)	1.27
Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU	
SNR _{max}	43
SNR _{max} (dB)	32.7
SNR _{max} (bits)	5.4
$1/\text{SNR}_{\text{max}}$ (%)	2.33
PRNU ₁₂₈₈ (%)	3.398
Nonlinearity	
LE (%)	0.34
Sensitivity & saturation	
$\mu_{p,\text{min}}$ (p)	9.37
$\mu_{p,\text{min}}$ (p/ μm^2)	3.3611
$\mu_{e,\text{min}}$ (e)	4.09
$\mu_{p,\text{sat}}$ (p)	4219
$\mu_{p,\text{sat}}$ (p/ μm^2)	1513
$\mu_{e,\text{sat}}$ (e)	1841
Dynamic range	
DR	450
DR (dB)	53.1
DR (bit)	8.8
Dark current	
$\mu_{c,\text{mean}}$ (DN/s)	—
$\mu_{c,\text{mean}}$ (e/s)	—
$\mu_{c,\text{var}}$ (e/s)	—

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 3

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	0.0 dB, 24.0
Exposure time	50.0 ms	Environmental temperature	22.2°C
Frame rate	14.0 Hz	Camera temperature	30.6°C
Data transfer mode	Mono 12	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	629 nm, 13.0 nm

Quantum efficiency	
η	0.255
Gain	
K (DN/e)	1.827
$1/K$ (e/DN)	0.547
Dark noise & DSNU	
$\sigma_{y,\text{dark}}$ (DN)	6.50
σ_d (e)	3.6
DSNU ₁₂₈₈ (DN)	2.32
DSNU ₁₂₈₈ (e)	1.27
Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU	
SNR _{max}	43
SNR _{max} (dB)	32.7
SNR _{max} (bits)	5.4
$1/\text{SNR}_{\text{max}}$ (%)	2.30
PRNU ₁₂₈₈ (%)	3.659
Nonlinearity	
LE (%)	0.49
Sensitivity & saturation	
$\mu_{p,\text{min}}$ (p)	16.08
$\mu_{p,\text{min}}$ (p/ μm^2)	5.7673
$\mu_{e,\text{min}}$ (e)	4.09
$\mu_{p,\text{sat}}$ (p)	7398
$\mu_{p,\text{sat}}$ (p/ μm^2)	2653
$\mu_{e,\text{sat}}$ (e)	1883
Dynamic range	
DR	460
DR (dB)	53.3
DR (bit)	8.8
Dark current	
$\mu_{c,\text{mean}}$ (DN/s)	—
$\mu_{c,\text{mean}}$ (e/s)	—
$\mu_{c,\text{var}}$ (e/s)	—

Detailed Data Operating Point 1, 467 nm

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1.1 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0003):

1.000	-0.000	0.027	0.000	0.028	-0.001	0.028	-0.001	0.027
-0.001	-0.002	0.001	-0.001	0.001	-0.002	0.001	-0.001	0.000
0.019	-0.000	0.002	-0.000	0.002	-0.000	0.002	0.000	0.001
0.000	-0.001	0.000	-0.001	0.000	-0.001	-0.000	-0.001	-0.000
0.018	-0.001	0.001	-0.001	0.001	-0.001	0.001	-0.001	0.000
-0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.001	-0.001	-0.000	-0.000	0.000
0.018	-0.001	0.001	-0.001	0.001	-0.001	0.002	-0.000	0.001
-0.000	-0.001	0.000	-0.001	0.000	-0.002	0.001	-0.002	-0.000
0.019	-0.001	0.001	-0.002	0.002	-0.001	0.002	-0.001	0.002

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0003):

1.000	0.002	-0.002	0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.001	-0.000	-0.001	0.000	0.000	-0.000
-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.001
0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000
-0.000	-0.001	0.000	-0.000	-0.001	0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000
-0.000	0.001	-0.001	0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000
-0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000
0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.001	-0.000	-0.000	0.000

1.2 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 201 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 201 illumination steps.

1.3 Linearity

Linearity curve.

Deviation from linearity.

1.4 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

1.5 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 17.0 - 30.9 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 7.6\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram of response image.

Vertical spectrogram of response image.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0545, 467nm, 30.10.2014

Horizontal lines PRNU m0545, 467nm, 30.10.2014

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Detailed Data Operating Point 2, 532 nm

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2.1 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0003):

1.000	0.001	0.025	-0.000	0.026	0.000	0.026	-0.000	0.026
-0.001	-0.001	0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000
0.018	-0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	-0.000	0.001
-0.001	0.001	-0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000
0.017	-0.001	0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.001	0.001
-0.000	-0.001	-0.001	-0.000	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
0.017	-0.001	0.001	-0.000	0.001	-0.000	0.001	-0.000	0.001
0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.018	-0.000	0.001	-0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0003):

1.000	0.003	-0.002	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.001
0.001	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000
-0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000
-0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.001	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000
-0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.001
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000

2.2 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 201 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 201 illumination steps.

2.3 Linearity

Linearity curve.

Deviation from linearity.

2.4 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

2.5 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 17.0 - 30.9 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 10.2\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram of response image.

Vertical spectrogram of response image.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0545, 532nm, 30.10.2014

Horizontal lines PRNU m0545, 532nm, 30.10.2014

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Detailed Data Operating Point 3, 629 nm

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3.1 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0003):

1.000	0.001	0.026	0.001	0.027	0.000	0.026	0.000	0.026
-0.001	-0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.001
0.016	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.001	0.000	-0.000	0.000
-0.001	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000
0.018	0.000	0.001	-0.000	0.001	-0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001
-0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	-0.001	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000
0.017	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000
-0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.001	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000
0.017	0.001	0.000	0.001	-0.000	0.001	-0.000	0.001	-0.000

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0003):

1.000	0.003	-0.002	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.001	0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000
0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000
0.000	0.001	-0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.001
0.001	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000
0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000
-0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
-0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.001	0.000
0.001	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	0.000

3.2 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 201 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 201 illumination steps.

3.3 Linearity

Linearity curve.

Deviation from linearity.

3.4 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

3.5 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 17.0 - 30.9 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 11.0\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram of response image.

Vertical spectrogram of response image.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0545, 629nm, 30.10.2014

Horizontal lines PRNU m0545, 629nm, 30.10.2014

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Dark Current

Mean of dark signal versus exposure time.

Variance of dark signal versus exposure time.

Spatial variation of dark current (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of dark current in e⁻/s from mean values

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of dark current in e⁻/s from variance

Comments

Basler has not yet published a data sheet from this camera.